

An introduction to cluster analysis using Empirical Logic

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Abstract. Empirical logic is a new soft computing method that proves useful for a variety of practical applications. Its bionic-inspired approach with easy-to-understand and collectively executed rules is the basis for a new approach to cluster analysis that is fundamentally different from traditional methods. In contrast to classical hierarchical or partitioning methods of cluster analysis (e.g. k-means), no algorithm is used here, but the groupings of the classification objects are determined by exploiting the phenomenon of emergence (self-organized structure formation), which can be observed during the virtually simultaneous execution of the rules.

Keywords: Cluster analysis, Empirical logic, Soft computing, Approximate reasoning, Bio-inspired computing, Nature-inspired computing

1 Introduction

Empirical logic is a novel soft computing method based on a bionic-inspired approach. For a detailed description, see the doctoral thesis of the author [1]. Similar to machine learning with the help of “artificial neural networks”, the biological model is the neural structure of the brain. Unlike machine learning, empirical logic does not consider the ability of neural networks to learn through structural adjustments of the connections between nerve cells. Rather, it takes advantage of the fact that the input received via the sensory organs causes the cerebral nervous system to transition to an energetically favorable equilibrium state after a dynamic transient phase, whereby the distribution of stimulated brain regions which is then assumed represents the output of this neuronal transfer function, which is referred to as cognitive sensory perception. In the 1980s, neuroscientists David D. Tank and John J. Hopfield (Nobel Prize in Physics 2024 shared with Geoffrey Hinton) employed electronic operational amplifiers connected to artificial neural networks to demonstrate that this effect can also be used to solve complex optimization problems [2]. Empirical logic is a formal computer-aided language that makes it possible to store empirical knowledge formulated on the basis of rules in a program structure modeled on a biological neural network, where the effect observed by Tank and Hopfield can be used to deal with challenging problems like cluster analysis. With the help of the computer algebra system Maple [3, p. 998 ff.], the author has built a prototype of an empirical logic program library and tested it using several practical application examples from business administration, economics, operations research and control engineering [4].

2 Some principles of Empirical Logic (EL)

The following remarks serve to recall the foundations of empirical logic as presented in “*Thinking fast: a bionic approach to soft computing*” [5], which prior reading is strongly recommended.

The basic mechanism of a nervous system consists in the directed point-to-point transmission of signals of different intensity between nerve cells or *neurons*. The contact points between the nerve cells, known as *synapses*, play a key role because they determine whether the activity of the signal-receiving nerve cell is *excited* or *inhibited*.

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This signal communication principle is also reflected in the basic concepts of empirical logic:

1. Notions that we use to mentally organize the information we perceive from our environment, such as facts, individuals, observed characteristics, actions, decisions, etc., are abstracted by empirical logic into the concept of a *category*. Analogously to the excitation state of a neuron, a category has a dynamic state called *validity* that is usually measured on a sliding scale $\mathbb{V} = [-1, 1] \subset \mathbb{R}$, such that +1 (-1) corresponds to the meaning “The fact does (not) belong to this category”. *Bound (free) categories* are (not) bound to a scalable reference magnitude. The empirical logic method distinguishes four standardized validity functions to characterize a bound category:
 - Threshold function (*e_THRESHOLD*)
 - Limitation function (*e_LIMITATION*)
 - Interval function (*e_INTERVAL*)
 - Estimation function (*e_ESTIMATION*)

For each of these validity functions, there is also a corresponding inverse function defined (e.g. *e_THRESHOLD_INVERSE*).

2. The *paradigm of circumstantial evidence* forms the semantic basis model of empirical logic, where both *pro-* and *contra-indications* and *hypotheses* are represented by categories.
3. Asserting a category validity (e.g. approving a hypothesis) is represented by the *e_VALIDATE* operator and corresponds to an *excitatory synapse*.
4. Refuting a category validity (e.g. disproving a hypothesis) is represented by the *e_INVALIDATE* operator and corresponds to an *inhibitory synapse*.

3 A simple application example

Cluster analysis is one of the multivariate methods of exploratory statistical data analysis. It is used to uncover intrinsic structures in large data sets by grouping classification objects that are similar based on their characteristics, such as companies, products, buyers, etc., into so-called clusters [6] [7, p. 78ff]. This method is particularly useful when the data set under investigation is very heterogeneous, so that common statistical parameters such as mean or variance are of little significance as indicators for the entire survey. Clustering therefore attempts to partition the data set into groups with greater homogeneity (intragroup homogeneity) [8]. Using a deliberately simple economic question, the following sections show that empirical logic is well suited to this task.

The application example concerns the relationship between unemployment and national debt in the eurozone for the year 2018 [9]. The set of classification objects to be partitioned into clusters therefore consists of the 19 countries of the European Community with the euro currency (EU 19) (cf. **Tab. 1** and **Fig. 1**). Assuming that each of these countries can form the potential crystallization point (or “cluster reference object”) for a cluster, the cluster analysis presents itself as a combinatorial assignment problem between the “EU 19” countries and the maximum of 19 cluster reference objects. If the assignment decisions are denoted by $x_{ij} \in \{0, 1\}$, the combinatorial problem does not consist of a one-to-one allocation, but several of the $m = 19$ countries i may be assigned to the same cluster j :

$$\sum_{i=1}^m x_{ij} \leq m$$

Conversely, each country i must belong to exactly one cluster j :

$$\sum_{j=1}^m x_{ij} = 1$$

No.	Eurozone countries (EU 19)	National debt in % of GDP 2018	Unemployment rate in % May 2018
1	Belgium	101,50	6,00
2	Germany	60,20	3,40
3	Estonia	8,80	5,00
4	Finland	60,40	7,90
5	France	96,40	9,20
6	Greece	177,80	20,10
7	Ireland	65,60	5,30
8	Italy	130,70	10,70
9	Latvia	37,00	7,40
10	Lithuania	36,00	6,80
11	Luxembourg	22,60	5,20
12	Malta	47,10	3,90
13	Netherlands	53,50	3,90
14	Austria	74,80	4,60
15	Portugal	122,50	7,30
16	Slovakia	49,00	6,80
17	Slovenia	69,30	5,60
18	Spain	97,60	15,80
19	Cyprus	105,70	8,40

Tab. 1: Data set of the application example

Fig. 1: Data set of the application example (scatter plot)

4 The pursued approach

The approach pursued here is based on the following conceptual model: According to *Coulomb's law* of electrostatics, it is well known that two unlike charges Q_1 and Q_2 attract each other with a force F that is inversely proportional to their distance r [10, pp. 19-27]:

$$F = \frac{Q_1 Q_2}{4\pi\epsilon r^2}$$

Analogously, it is assumed that the classification objects of a cluster analysis task also exert mutual forces of attraction on each other which are inversely proportional to their distance measure. Accordingly, the “attractive force” of a cluster reference object is all the greater, the larger the number of “neighboring” or “similar” classification objects is. It is therefore assumed that the classification objects grouped together in a cluster do not have a “small distance” to each other by chance, but that this arrangement is a causal consequence of the fictitious and yet to be determined force of attraction of the cluster reference object (see section 6.1.2 below).

Based on the conceptual system introduced by the pioneering Dutch computer scientist Gerrit Blaauw [11], the following sections first present the functional appearance of cluster analysis from the user's perspective (the *system architecture*) and then the internal functional system structure (the *system implementation*). However, a detailed explanation of the *system realization* as a prototype using the computer algebra system Maple is deliberately omitted [1, pp. 149-162; 353-360].

5 Architecture of the cluster analysis system

The software of a cluster analysis program implemented with empirical logic always requires at least three information objects as input:

1. Data set of classification objects
2. Parameter for determining the “attractive force” of the cluster reference objects
3. Maximum number of empirical logic rule iterations if no feasible solution is found

The data set typically consists of a table:

$$Dataset = (attr_{ij})_{m,n} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$$

This is conveniently represented as a matrix such that each row contains the attribute values of the n characteristic features for m classification objects. For the example with the 19 countries of the European Community with the euro currency, the data matrix looks like (Fig. 2):

$$Dataset := \begin{bmatrix} 101.5 & 6.0 \\ 60.2 & 3.4 \\ 8.8 & 5.0 \\ 60.4 & 7.9 \\ 96.4 & 9.2 \\ 177.8 & 20.1 \\ 65.6 & 5.3 \\ 130.7 & 10.7 \\ 37.0 & 7.4 \\ 36.0 & 6.8 \\ 22.6 & 5.2 \\ 47.1 & 3.9 \\ 53.5 & 3.9 \\ 74.8 & 4.6 \\ 122.5 & 7.3 \\ 49.0 & 6.8 \\ 69.3 & 5.6 \\ 97.6 & 15.8 \\ 105.7 & 8.4 \end{bmatrix}$$

Fig. 2: Data matrix

A user-defined parameter *CARC* (= Cluster Attraction Range Coefficient) determines the strength of the “attraction force” with which the cluster reference objects act on “neighboring” or “similar” classification objects. It is specified as a number from the interval $[0, 1]$ according to the range between minimum and maximum attractive force. Together with another user-defined parameter for the maximum number of rule iterations, the call to the prototype developed with Maple is as follows:

$$ExecuteClusterAnalysis(Dataset, CARC, maxIterations)$$

The program execution result consists of three elements, including a return code *RC*, the number of required rule executions, and a cluster assignment matrix. The respective meanings of the return codes are listed in **Tab. 2**.

Note that the return code $RC = -2$ means that with a large value of the parameter $maxIterations$, a possibly futile search for a valid cluster partitioning was aborted prematurely, since no change in the validity values of the cluster assignment matrix is detectable upon further execution of the empirical logic rules, and the system is apparently close to a stationary equilibrium.

RC	Meaning
0	Regular termination of program execution with a valid cluster partitioning
-1	Abnormal termination of program execution without a valid cluster partitioning after reaching the specified maximum number of rule iterations
-2	Abnormal termination of program execution without a valid cluster partitioning if no significant change in the cluster assignment matrix can be detected upon further repetition of the rule executions

Tab. 2: Return codes of the Maple program ExecuteClusterAnalysis

The returned cluster assignment matrix $D = (d_{ij})_{m,m} \in \mathbb{V}^{m \times m}$ has a quadratic structure. For each classification object i , it indicates the validity of the decision $d_{ij} \in \mathbb{V}$ with which it was assigned to the cluster reference object j . Figures **Fig. 3** to **Fig. 6** graphically show the cluster assignment matrix as a bar chart for several different values of the parameter $CARC$. The corresponding clusters are marked with a dashed line in the data set shown as a scatter plot. The cluster reference object located in the center of each cluster is highlighted in red. Arrows indicate the directions of the respective attractive forces.

Fig. 3: Result of a cluster analysis with $CARC = 0.3$

Fig. 4: Result of a cluster analysis with $CARC = 0.6$

Fig. 5: Result of a cluster analysis with $CARC = 0.9$

Fig. 6: Result of a cluster analysis with $CARC = 1.0$

Note that the result of the cluster analysis for $CARC = 0.3$ (cf. **Fig. 3**) is formally invalid according to the criteria mentioned in section 3, since countries 6 (Greece) and 18 (Spain) could not be assigned to any cluster. Although the program was terminated after reaching a steady state with the return code $RC = -2$ (cf. **Tab. 2**), the partitioning into three clusters and two “special cases” obviously offers the greatest meaningfulness for a more detailed fiscal and employment policy assessment of the year 2018 compared to the other cluster formations (Figures **Fig. 4** to **Fig. 6**). The missing assignment of Greece and Spain to any cluster can be explained by the fact that with the set parameter value $CARC = 0.3$, the two classification criteria unemployment rate and national debt differ too much from the values of the other countries in the eurozone to form a homogeneous group of countries. Only when the $CARC$ parameter value continues to rise can a positive “attractive force” be observed, either acting on these two countries or emanating from them as cluster reference objects.

Additionally, it should be mentioned that in **Fig. 5**, the positive validity achieved for cluster reference object 6 (Greece) is too small to be visible in the bar chart shown on the left hand side.

6 Implementation of the cluster analysis system

For the implementation of the cluster analysis system prototype, it has proven useful to reuse the internal structure of another system implemented with empirical logic to solve the “book sorting problem” (cf. chapter 4 in the above mentioned paper by the author “*Thinking fast: a bionic approach to soft computing*”) and to adapt it to the specific requirements of the task at hand [5]. For a better understanding of the following sections, it may be useful to first study the explanations given there.

As a general note, it should be mentioned that the results of a cluster analysis shown above in section 5 (see figures **Fig. 3** to **Fig. 6**) were obtained with implementations of the empirical logic operators as listed in **Tab. 3** [1, p. 155] [5]:

EL-Operators	Implementation
e_AND	generalized mean with parameter $e_P = -0.5$
e_OR	generalized mean with parameter $e_P = -0.5$
$e_VALIDATE$	Einstein sum
$e_INVALIDATE$	Einstein product

Tab. 3: Empirical logic operator implementations used for cluster analysis

The implementation of the cluster analysis system architecture outlined in section 5 consists of the following procedural steps:

1. Determine a “feature distance matrix” for each classification feature.
2. Determine a “categorized feature matrix” for each feature distance matrix by applying the validity function of the bound category “small distance”.
3. Combine the categorized feature distance matrices into a “categorized data set matrix” using the empirical logic operator e_AND .
4. Determine the attractive force value for each potential cluster reference object.
5. Interpret the attractive force values as validity values of the free category “great attractive force”.
6. Turn the categorized data set matrix into an “assignment preference matrix” by replacing its diagonal elements with the validity values of the category “great attractive force”.
7. Apply the cluster analysis empirical rules to the assignment preference matrix.

The details of these operations are discussed in the following sections.

6.1 The categories of assignment preferences

6.1.1 The category “small distance”

According to step 1 of the procedure described above, a symmetric feature distance matrix

$$(\Delta_{ij}^k)_{m,m} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$$

must be determined for each of the $k = 1 \dots n$ columns of the data set matrix. Their entries represent the reference magnitudes for the category “small distance”, which are formed on the set of m classification objects for the feature k by the relation

$$P_k = (p_{ij}^k)_{m,m} \in \mathbb{V}^{m \times m} \text{ with } p_{ij}^k = e_LIMITATION(\Delta_{ij}^k, l_k, f_k)$$

Its meaning is:

“Classification object i has a small distance to classification object j with respect to feature k .”

The parameters l_k (= validity limit) and f_k (= fuzziness) required for the limiting function $e_LIMITATION$ are calculated for each k according to the following formulas:

$$l_k = \frac{CARC \cdot \max_{i \neq j}(\Delta_{ij}^k) + (2 - CARC) \cdot \min_{i \neq j}(\Delta_{ij}^k)}{2}$$

$$f_k = \max \left(CARC \cdot \frac{\max_{i \neq j}(\Delta_{ij}^k) - \min_{i \neq j}(\Delta_{ij}^k)}{6}, f_{min} \right) \text{ with } f_{min} > 0$$

The minimum fuzziness value f_{min} ensures that the invalid value $f_k = 0$ cannot occur (e.g.: $f_{min} = 0.001$). **Fig. 7** and **Fig. 8** show that a change in the range of the “attractive forces” of the cluster reference objects using the $CARC$ parameter causes a corresponding parallel shift of the validity limit l_k and an adjustment of the fuzziness f_k in the validity function graph of the respective “small distance” category.

Fig. 7: Validity function graphs of the bound category “small distance” (national debt)

Fig. 8: Validity function graphs of the bound category “small distance” (unemployment rate)

Fig. 9: Determine “small distances” between national debts

Fig. 10: Determine “small distances” between unemployment rates

Fig. 11: Determine “small distances” between classification objects (eurozone countries)

Fig. 9 and Fig. 10 illustrate in bar charts how the categorized feature matrices are derived from the distance matrices using the validity function of the bound category “small distance” for parameter value $CARC = 0.3$ as an example (cf. step 2 of the implementation procedure). Fig. 11 shows how the empirical logic operator e_AND serves to combine the $k = 1 \dots n$ categorized feature matrices (relations P_k) into a general relation on the set of m classification objects as an n -fold bound category (cf. implementation step 3):

$$P = (p_{ij})_{m,m} \in \mathbb{V}^{m \times m}$$

The resulting categorized data set matrix assesses the validity of the statement

“Classification object i has a small distance to classification object j .”

An equivalent formulation is: “The classification objects i and j are similar”.

6.1.2 The category “great attractive force”

Fig. 11 also shows that the diagonal elements p_{ii} of the category “small distance” always have a validity value $1 = e_TRUE$, because each classification object has no distance to itself. This means that, due to their lack of distinguishability, they have no usable significance for the empirical rules of cluster analysis described below in section 6.3. However, this deficiency can be remedied by replacing the diagonal elements with the validity

values of another assignment preference with the meaning “great attractive force”. For each classification object as a free category, this expresses the extent to which it is suited to be a “power center” or as a cluster reference object binding classification objects located at a “small distance” to itself as cluster elements.

Fig. 12: Calculating the validity values of category “great attractive force”

Fig. 13: Determine the assignment preference matrix

The following procedure has proven useful for calculating the corresponding validity values (cf. Fig. 12, Fig. 13, and steps 4 to 6 of the implementation procedure):

- 1) For each row i of the matrix $P = (p_{ij})_{m,m} \in \mathbb{V}^{m \times m}$, determine the sum of the validity values with $p_{ij} > 0$ without considering the diagonal element p_{ii} :

$$P_i^+ = \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq i}}^m p_{ij} \quad \text{with } p_{ij} > e_UNKNOWN() = 0$$

- 2) Scale the determined validity sums to the validity interval $[0, 1]$:

$$P_i^{[0,1]} = \frac{P_i^+}{\max\{P_i^+\}} \quad \text{for } i = 1 \dots m$$

- 3) Transform the scaled validity sums to the interval $[-1, 1]$ using the mapping $R: [0, 1] \rightarrow [-1, 1]$ and $R(v) = 2v - 1$:

$$P_i^{[-1, 1]} = R(P_i^{[0,1]}) \quad \text{for } i = 1 \dots m$$

- 4) Replace the diagonal elements of the matrix P by the validity values calculated in step 3) with the new meaning:

“Classification object i has a great attractive force as a cluster reference object”

6.2 The category of assignment decisions

The cluster assignment matrix $D = (d_{ij})_{m,m} \in \mathbb{V}^{m \times m}$ already mentioned in section 5 represents, as a free category (see section 2), the totality of the assignment decisions between the classification objects and those classification objects that were selected as cluster reference objects during the cluster analysis. In the initial state, these have the validity value $e_UNKNOWN()$, i.e., the value 0. During the cluster analysis, as the empirical rules described below are iterated, the validity values grow and shrink seemingly chaotically with a non-monotonic and non-linear dynamics until the termination criterion mentioned later in section 6.4 is met (cf. bar charts in **Fig. 14**). This shows that a concomitant phenomenon of the collective interactions of rule execution is the phenomenon of the spontaneous formation of order structures, which is known as *emergence*.

Fig. 14: Validity of assignment decisions during the execution of the cluster analysis

6.3 The empirical rules of cluster analysis

In contrast to conventional cluster analysis methods, the empirical rules of cluster analysis do not serve to pursue the solution strategy of an algorithmic procedure but only describe the required properties of a “permissible” cluster partitioning, which is much simpler to achieve. Due to the assignment preferences “small distance” and “great attractive force” combined in the assignment preference matrix P (cf. section 6.1.2), corresponding case distinctions must be taken into account in the rules (see **Tab. 4** and **Tab. 5**).

Validation rule ($i = j$)	IF	object i has a great attractive force as a cluster reference object
	AND	object i is not already assigned to another cluster k
	THEN	validate the decision to select object i as a cluster reference object.
Invalidation rule ($i = j$)	IF	object i has not a great attractive force as a cluster reference object
	OR	object i is already assigned to another cluster k
	THEN	invalidate the decision to select object i as a cluster reference object.

Tab. 4: Empirical logic rules for the diagonal elements of the assignment preference matrix

Validation rule ($i \neq j$)	IF	object i and object j are similar
	AND	object j is a cluster reference object
	AND	object i is not already assigned to another cluster k
	THEN	validate the decision that object i is assigned to cluster j .
Invalidation rule ($i \neq j$)	IF	object i and object j are not similar
	OR	object j is not a cluster reference object
	OR	object i is already assigned to another cluster k
	THEN	invalidate the decision that object i is assigned to cluster j .

Tab. 5: Empirical logic rules for the off-diagonal elements of the assignment preference matrix

The formal description of the rules using the empirical logic operators for the diagonal elements $i = 1 \dots m$ of the assignment preference matrix $P = (p_{ij})_{m,m} \in \mathbb{V}^{m \times m}$ and the cluster assignment matrix $D = (d_{ij})_{m,m} \in \mathbb{V}^{m \times m}$ with $i \notin \{k_1, k_2, \dots, k_{m-1}\}$ is as follows:

$$d_{ii}^{t+1} := e_VALIDATE(e_AND(p_{ii}, e_NOT(d_{ik_1}^t, d_{ik_2}^t, \dots, d_{ik_{m-1}}^t)), d_{ii}^t)$$

$$d_{ii}^{t+1} := e_INVALIDATE(e_OR(e_NOT(p_{ii}), d_{ik_1}^t, d_{ik_2}^t, \dots, d_{ik_{m-1}}^t), d_{ii}^t)$$

Here, d_{ii}^t and d_{ii}^{t+1} denote the validity values of the assignment decisions at the times before and after the execution of the rules.

The corresponding formalization of the rules for the off-diagonal elements of the two matrices has this appearance:

$$d_{ij}^{t+1} := e_VALIDATE(e_AND(p_{ij}, p_{jj}, e_NOT(d_{ik_1}^t, d_{ik_2}^t, \dots, d_{ik_{m-1}}^t)), d_{ij}^t)$$

$$d_{ij}^{t+1} := e_INVALIDATE(e_OR(e_NOT(p_{ij}), e_NOT(p_{jj}), d_{ik_1}^t, d_{ik_2}^t, \dots, d_{ik_{m-1}}^t), d_{ij}^t)$$

The entirety of these validation and invalidation rules forms a network structure of collectively interacting assignment decisions. However, some precautions must be taken in the implementation of the rules, so that the principle of collective interaction is correctly reflected:

- 1) It is allowed and useful to first apply all validation rules and then all invalidation rules to the assignment decisions d_{ij} in each iteration phase t .
- 2) However, it is not permissible to execute the rules on one and the same cluster assignment matrix $D^t = (d_{ij}^t)_{m,m} \in \mathbb{V}^{m \times m}$, because then the new validity values of the assignment decisions would depend on the execution order and would be distorted. Therefore, it is necessary to explicitly provide a second matrix data structure $D^{t+1} = (d_{ij}^{t+1})_{m,m} \in \mathbb{V}^{m \times m}$, which takes the results calculated from iteration phase t . In the iteration step $t + 1$, the two data structures exchange their roles, which is also referred to as *swapping* in software terminology.

6.4 The termination criterion for the rule iterations

The application of the empirical rules of cluster analysis has a certain similarity to a *production system*. This term refers to a well-known architecture of knowledge-based systems, the functional principles of which are described in great detail for example in [12]. However, there are some essential differences:

The empirical logic rules are always executed collectively (i.e., virtually “simultaneously”). In a production system, on the other hand, the set of selectable rules (the so-called *conflict set*) is redetermined in each iteration step, and then only one rule is executed. While the inference engine of a production system stops its activity as soon as the conflict set no longer contains any rules, the control flow for the empirical logic rules requires a termination criterion. Otherwise, their application would never end and the change in the data involved (validity values of the category of assignment decisions) would lead to a “saturation state”. **Tab. 2** in section 5 already mentioned the situations in which the execution of the cluster analysis is interrupted and the program is terminated with a corresponding return code $RC \in \{0, -1, -2\}$:

- 1) A valid cluster partitioning was found.
- 2) No valid cluster partitioning was found or formulated in the terminology of circumstantial evidence (see section 2): The hypotheses formulated in the empirical rules of cluster analysis above could neither be proven nor refuted ($RC = -1$ or $RC = -2$).

A valid cluster partitioning is given when each of the m classification objects is assigned to exactly one of $k \leq m$ clusters. In particular, it must be ensured that the cluster reference object also belongs to the cluster it represents.

The implementation of the termination criterion uses a function $Norm: \mathbb{V} \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ which normalizes the cluster assignment matrix $D = (d_{ij})_{m,m} \in \mathbb{V}^{m \times m}$ after each iteration step of the rule execution so that it contains only zeros and ones:

$$Norm(d_{ij}) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } d_{ij} > e_UNKNOWN() \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

The actual test of the termination criterion then consists of the following two comparisons:

$$\forall i = 1 \dots m: 1 = \sum_{j=1}^m Norm(d_{ij})$$

$$Norm(d_{ij}) = 1 \Rightarrow Norm(d_{jj}) = 1$$

7 Summary

Just like traditional cluster analysis methods, cluster analysis with the help of empirical logic is suitable for solving the statistical problem of strong heterogeneity in a survey population. By breaking down the collected data into groups (clusters) with high intragroup homogeneity and high intergroup heterogeneity, the conditions are created for statistical analyses that provide meaningful results for each survey group [8, p. 490].

In addition to demonstrating another possible application of empirical logic, the above explanations also present an innovative method of cluster analysis, the properties of which differ significantly from classical hierarchical and partitioning clustering methods:

1. Instead of selecting suitable proximity or similarity measures, the category “small distance” is used, which can be represented using the limitation function $e_LIMITATION$ and is linked to the characteristic features of the classification objects. A conjunctive operation using the empirical logical operator e_AND enables the representation of multiple bound categories when more than one classification feature is present. Practical test examples have shown that in addition to cardinal classification features, nominal (especially dichotomous) classification features can also be taken into account without special coding measures [8, p. 552].
2. Instead of a fusion algorithm, a dynamic self-organization process (phenomenon of *emergence*) takes place, in the course of which the “permissible” cluster constellations described with the help of empirical logic rules establish the state of a stationary equilibrium of “attractive forces”. The driving force is a free category called “great attractive force”, which is derived from the category validity values of classification objects that are located at a “small distance” to a potential cluster reference object. The “degree of fineness” of the partitioning can be influenced by the user via a parameter $CARC$ (= Cluster Attraction Range Coefficient). However, unlike hierarchical clustering methods, a monotonic sequence of $CARC$ parameter values does not guarantee a monotonic sequence of refinements (or coarsening) of the partitions. This is due to the fact that the method presented here is not a “stepwise constructive” procedure, which requires a hierarchical arrangement of the partitions. Rather, the clusters determined using empirical logic result completely independently for each $CARC$ parameter value specified by the user. This means that a graphical illustration of the heterogeneity measure of a certain number of clusters using a dendrogram is either not possible or

only coincidentally agrees with the results of a cluster analysis carried out according to the method of empirical logic.

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